

1 **HPV E5 controls expression of ABC transporters, activating their expression in the absence of**
2 **other HPV gene products and prior to transformation.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8
9 Citations

- 10
11 1. Ren, S., Gaykalova, D.A., Guo, T., Favorov, A.V., Fertig, E.J., Tamayo, P., Callejas-Valera, J.L.,
12 Allevato, M., Gilardi, M., Santos, J. and Fukusumi, T., 2020. HPV E2, E4, E5 drive alternative carcinogenic
13 pathways in HPV positive cancers. *Oncogene*, 39(40), pp.6327-6339.
- 14 2. Ilahi, N.E. and Bhatti, A., 2020. Impact of HPV E5 on viral life cycle via EGFR signaling. *Microbial*
15 *pathogenesis*, 139, p.103923.
- 16 3. Stöppler, M.C., Straight, S.W., Tsao, G., Schlegel, R. and Mccance, D.J., 1996. The E5 gene of
17 HPV-16 enhances keratinocyte immortalization by full-length DNA. *Virology*, 223(1), pp.251-254.
- 18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28